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**THE IMPACT OF RURAL-URBAN SCHOOL LOCATION ON STUDENTS' READING
HABIT IN SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS OF OGUN STATE OF
NIGERIA**

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Abstract

Poor academic performance remains one of the persistent challenges, confronting the education sector, and it has been widely attributed to students' poor reading habits, particularly at the secondary school level. Although numerous studies have examined reading practices, few have focused specifically on reading habits, and even fewer have compared the relationship between reading habits and the conduciveness of reading environment in rural and urban schools. This study, therefore, examined the differences between rural and urban secondary school students in terms of their reading habits and conduciveness of their school environments to reading. Grounded in the Reading Engagement Theory – which posits that emotional connectivity influences reading behaviour – the study employed a descriptive survey design. Two sets of questionnaires were administered: one to students and another to teachers, responsible for teaching reading. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics (tables and percentages) and an independent samples *t*-test at 0.05 level of significance. Findings indicated no significant difference in the reading habits of rural and urban students. The study concluded that poor reading habits among secondary school students are not necessarily determined by school location. Moreover, students across both settings are similarly affected by environmental distractions that hinder effective reading.

Keywords: reading habits, school environment, rural-urban comparison, secondary school students, Reading Engagement Theory

Introduction

Reading and education are inseparable. The former, which is one of the four main language skills, is receptive in nature and a literacy skill. It involves letter, word, and meaning identifications to decode encoded messages in the form of text. Reading is associated with numerous benefits that every modern human needs to maximise. Notwithstanding, the attitudes of Nigerians to reading generally are not encouraging. The worst aspect is students' unfavourable disposition towards reading, courtesy of many apparent factors. Among them are: inadequate/ lack of motivation of learners and their teachers, teachers' non-possession of zeal to foster reading skills, students' access to technological advancement such as internet and mobile phone, non-conducive environment, lackadaisical attitudes of some guardians and parents on the education of their wards and children among others. This poor attitude can result in poor reading habits, which subsequently leads to students' persistent high failure rates in examinations, increase in school drop-out rate, poverty, production of unskilled manpower, high rate of illiteracy, frustration and loss of self-esteem.

Reading which transcends the recognition of graphic or printed signals and the ability to recognise individual words, phrases, clauses and sentences is very imperative for success in schools for the child's growth and development as well as for success in later years as an adult. According to Mabekoje (2009), reading is the solid foundation upon which the totality of learning process and literacy enhancement rest on. At this age, learning and literacy can never be eschewed. In summary, reading is inevitable for survival in the modern world of ours.

Experts describe this bothersome development as a situation that will cause serious glitches for the country in the future (Chika, 2009 & Sanders, 2007). Poor reading habits will lead to adverse consequences individually and collectively. Effective reading on the part of secondary school students, with extraneous variables put on hold, leads to academic excellence. According to Sanders (2007), reading draws out the creativity in the child. Many parents believe that students in urban-based secondary schools have an edge academically over their rural-based counterparts. Against all odds, some 'enlightened' parents and guardians, in rural settings, inconveniently send their children and wards to secondary schools that are located in urban centres. These are the stimulants of this study.

Unfavourable disposition towards reading breeds worthless education and subsequently leads to stunted individual and societal developments. In public discourse, it is often asserted – though without sufficient empirical verification – that students in urban-based secondary schools exhibit

a more favourable disposition towards reading than their counterparts in rural-based schools. Hence, this study seeks to empirically substantiate this claim to examining whether significant differences exist between the two categories of students in their reading habits and conduciveness of their school environments to reading.

Literature Review/ Conceptual Clarifications

Reading is a large, complicated and ill-defined cognitive behaviour, which is very hard to be captured theoretically according to some scholars (Obanya, 2002; Snowling & Hulme, 2005; Durotoye, 2011; Akindele, 2016). Reading, one of the four basic language skills, is a literacy skill: it is concerned with the written medium. In addition, it is receptive like listening: it involves decoding messages. There are strong links between writing and reading: well-composed written/typed messages aid reading. A good reader will turn out to be a good writer. The complexity of reading skills comprises words and sentence processing, drawing inferences, dealing with novelty and controlling the process (Yisa, 2024). Mabekoje (2009) defines reading as a highly complex activity that includes various important aspects, such as recognising symbols quickly and accurately; and integrating them into definite thought and action patterns. Reading encompasses two symbiotic essential processes, which are visual and mental (or intellectual). This is because “the eye is used for visual perception of printed symbols while the mind is used for interpretation of what has been read” (Mabekoje, 2009: 91). He goes further to say that certain essential features must exist before actual reading can take place. They are as follows:

- (a) Proper identification of letters and the sounds they stand for (word cognition),
- (b) Assigning correct meaning to what has been read since the primary reason behind reading is to extract information from a text (comprehension),
- (c) Reacting to what has been read (reaction),
- (d) Fusing the earlier and current materials (fusion),
- (e) Application of appropriate reading rates and skills (rates) and
- (f) Putting what has been read into use (utilisation).

Reading Habits can be described as the individual routine manner one has developed to engage in reading text. Good reading habits boost vocabulary development, reading comprehension and good academic performance. Confirming this from a study, Oyediran (2019) discovers a positive

correlation between reading habits and academic success. Regular reading, diverse reading materials, active reading and purposeful reading make up good reading habits. Aina (2012) discovers that Nigerian secondary school students spend more time watching television at the expense of reading. Similarly, Ukpeyong (2017) realises that students prefer digital resources to print materials.

Reading Engagement Theory

John Guthrie and Allan Wigfield propounded Reading Engagement Theory (RET) in the late 1990s and early 2000s. It postulates that students' emotional connection to reading including other factors like interest, enjoyment and motivation influence their reading habits. It aligns with Gambrell's (1996) Reading Engagement Model, which stresses the position of interest, enjoyment and motivation in reading engagement. Interest and motivation lead to favourable disposition towards reading, which results to good reading habit and academic success (Krashen, 2004; Wigfield & Guthrie, 1997 and Wigfield & Guthrie 2000). RET is relevant to this study: it proposes that reading engagement comprises cognitive, emotional and behavioural aspects, which offer a background for grasping reader-text factors that enables stakeholders to nurture students' reading habits (Gambrell, 1996; Krashen, 2004; Guthrie & Wigfield, 2000; and Hidi & Renninger, 2006).

Research Hypotheses

- (i) There is a significant difference between the reading habits of students in rural-based and urban-based secondary schools.
- (ii) There is a significant difference between conduciveness of rural based schools to reading and that of urban located schools.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design, suitable for examining existing conditions without manipulating variables. It focuses on identifying differences in students' reading habits and the conduciveness of their school environment. Participants include students and their teachers from rural and urban secondary schools in Ogun State. Using stratified random sampling, 12 schools were selected from three local government areas – Abeokuta North, Abeokuta South, and Obafemi-Owode. From each school, 25 SS 2 students were randomly chosen, given a total of 300 students and 12 teachers.

Data were collected, using two validated questionnaires – one for the students another for the teachers. Content validity was confirmed by experts in language education and educational evaluation. A pilot study conducted in one rural and urban school yielded Cronbach’s alpha coefficients of 0.529 and 0.541 for the students and teacher instruments respectively. The data analysed, using descriptive statistics (tables and percentages) and an independent samples *t*-test at a 0.05 significance level, with computations performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) for accuracy and efficiency.

Analyses: Student Respondents

Question 1: How many times do you read daily?

Table 1

	Frequency	Percentage
6 - 7 times	35	11.7
4 - 5 times	81	27.0
2 - 3 times	179	59.7
1 time	5	1.7
Total	300	100.0

From table 1 above, 11.7% of the respondents (students) claimed to read 6 - 7 times daily, 27% maintained that they read 4 – 5 times daily, 59.7% asserted that they read 2 – 3 times daily, while the remaining 1.7% claimed to read just once a day. From the information, we can presume that majority of the respondents read 2 – 3 times daily.

Question 2: How often do you read weekly?

Table 2

	Frequency	Percentage
6 - 7 days	60	20.0
4 - 5 days	61	20.3

2 - 3 days	114	38.0
1 day	28	9.3
Irregular	37	12.3
Total	300	100.0

From table 2 above, 20% of the respondents asserted that they read 6 – 7 days weekly, 20.3% claimed to read 4 – 5 days weekly, 38.0% maintained that they read 2 – 3 days weekly, 9.3% claimed to read just one day in a week, while the remaining 12.3% stated that they did not have any regular pattern of reading weekly. From this information, we can agree that majority of the respondents read 2 – 3 days weekly.

Question 3: What are the facilities that aid reading during school hours?

Table 3

	Frequency	Percentage
Library	171	57.0
Books	41	13.7
Conducive Environment	74	24.7
None	12	4.0
Others	2	0.7
Total	300	100.0

From table 3 above, 57% of the respondents (students) asserted that library facilities aided their reading during school hours, 13.7% claimed to be aided by books, 24.7% stated that they were aided by conducive environment, 4% claimed not to be aided by any of the aforementioned

facilities while the remaining 0.7% maintained that they were aided by other unmentioned facilities. From the information above, we can consent to the fact that majority of the respondents were aided by library facilities during school hours.

Question 6: Question 6 captured the number of times the respondents read voluntarily in a week. From the result, majority of the respondents claimed to read voluntarily between 5 and 6 times a week

Question 7: How many times does your parent/guardian ask you to read weekly?

Table 4

	Frequency	Percentage
6 - 7 times	72	24.0
4 - 5 times	110	36.7
2 - 3 times	82	27.3
1 time	8	2.7
Rarely	28	9.3
Total	300	100.0

From the information above, 24% of the respondents (students) claimed to have been urged by their parents/ guardians to read 6-7 times weekly and 36.7% stated that they were prevailed upon to read 4-5 times weekly. In addition, 27.3% claimed to have been encouraged to read 2-3 times weekly, 2.7% averred that they were urged to read once a week and the remaining 9.3% maintained that they were rarely asked to read. From this information, we can accept that majority of the respondents were usually urged by their parents/ guardians to read 4-5 times weekly.

Question 4: Do you experience distractions while reading in the school?

Table 5

	Frequency	Percent
YES	236	78.7
NO	64	21.3
Total	300	100.0

From table 5, 78.7% of the respondents asserted that experienced distractions while reading in the school, while the remaining 21.3% of the respondents claimed not to experience any distractions. We can therefore attest to the fact that majority of the respondents experienced distractions while reading in the school.

Question 5: Do you experience any of these while reading during the school hours?

Table 6

	Frequency	Percent
VEHICULAR NOISE	12	4.0
PARTY NOISE	4	1.3
NOISE FROM STUDENTS	275	91.7
NOISE FROM TEACHERS	2	.7
OTHERS	7	2.3
Total	300	100.0

From table 6, it was revealed that 4.0% of the respondents claimed to experience vehicular noise while reading during school hours, 1.3% of the respondents stated that they experienced party noise while reading, 91.7% of the respondents asserted they experienced noise from fellow students while reading, 0.7% of the respondents claimed to experience noise from teachers while reading, while the remaining 2.3% of the respondents averred that they experienced other forms of distractions while reading during the school hours. In conclusion, we are made to believe that majority of the respondents experience noise from students while reading during the school hours.

Analyses: Teacher Respondents

Question 6: Which reading facilities are available in your school?

Table 7

	Frequency	Percentage
Library	2	16.7
Books	10	83.3

Total	12	100.0
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Table 7 shows that 16.7% of the respondents claimed that library was available while the remaining 83.3% attested to availability of books. From this information, we can conclude that majority of the respondents were of the opinion that books were available for students to read.

Question 7: Is the school environment conducive for your students to read?

Table 8

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
YES	8	66.7
NO	3	25.0
MAY BE	1	8.3
TOTAL	12	100.0

Table 8 shows that 66.7% of the respondents claimed that the school environment was conducive, 25.0% of them disagreed to this while the remaining 8.3% responded that the school environment might be conducive for students to read. From this information, we can conclude that the school environment was conducive for the students to read.

Results: Testing for Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis One

H₀: There is no significant difference between the reading habit of students in rural based secondary schools and that of students in urban located schools.

H₁: There is a significant difference between the reading habit of students in rural based secondary schools and that of students in urban located schools.

Paired Sample T-test

Paired sample T-test is used to test whether the mean of one variable differs from another variable. When $P < 0.05$, the study concludes that the group mean is significantly different from the variable.

Table 9: Testing Hypothesis One

	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Df	T-calculated	T-critical	P	DECISION
Reading habit of students in rural-based schools	300	2.5133	.71987	299	-5.041	1.972	0.05	Accept the null hypothesis
Reading habit of students in urban-based schools		2.7367	1.23521					

From the above result analysis presented, it shows that the probability value is less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance. The t-calculated value is -5.041 and the t-critical is 1.972 at degree of freedom 299 using two-tailed significant level. The rule of thumb guiding the acceptability of a particular hypothesis in t-test is that when the t-calculated is greater than t-critical, we are to accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. On the other hand, if the critical value is greater than the calculated value, we are to accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternate hypothesis. Since the second condition is certified: as the calculated value is lesser than the critical value, we are therefore to accept the null hypothesis which states that **there is no significant difference between the reading habit of students in rural based secondary schools and that of students in urban located schools.**

Hypothesis Two

H₀: There is no significant difference between conduciveness of rural based schools to reading and that of urban located schools.

H₃: There is a significant difference between conduciveness of rural based schools to reading and that of urban located schools.

Paired Sample T-Test

Paired sample T-Test is used to test whether the mean of one variable differs from another variable. When $P < 0.05$ the researcher concludes the group mean is significantly different from the variable.

Table 10: Testing Hypothesis Two

	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Df	T-calculated	T-critical	P	DECISION
Conduciveness of school environment for reading in rural areas	300	1.5733	.49542	299	-30.287	1.972	0.05	Accept the null hypothesis
Conduciveness of school environment for reading in urban areas		3.0833	1.06151					

From the above result analysis presented, it shows that the probability value is less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance. The t-calculated value is -30.287 and the t-critical is 1.972 at degree of freedom 299, using two tailed significant level. The rule of thumb guiding the acceptability of a particular hypothesis in t-test is that when the t-calculated is greater than t-critical, we are to accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. Contrarily, if the critical value is greater than the calculated value, we are to accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternate hypothesis. Since the second condition is confirmed as the calculated value is lesser than the critical value, we are to accept the null hypothesis which states that **there is no significant difference between conduciveness to reading of rural based schools and that of urban located schools.**

Discussion of the Findings

The study focuses on secondary schools in selected Ogun State local governments to examine whether rural-urban location influences students' reading and the conduciveness of school environments. Despite its limitation, its findings have broader relevance, as Nigerian – and by extension African – students, as well as rural and urban settings, share common characteristics. The findings are as follows:

- i. Contrary to the initial assumption, the study revealed no significant difference in the reading habits of rural and urban secondary school students. Among rural students, 60% read two to three times daily, compared to 59.3% of urban students – a negligible 0.7% difference. Similarly, 21.3% of rural students and 18.7% of urban students read six to seven weekly, a slight 2.6% gap favouring rural learners. This minor variation may stem from urban students' engagement in other non-academic activities – such as internet browsing, watching of European football league matches, going to parties, visitation to friends among others – which would, no doubt, reduce the time and the number of days available for academic endeavours, significant of which is reading.
- ii. Contrary to the second hypothesis, the study found no significant difference in the conduciveness between rural and urban schools. Equal proportion of teachers in both settings (66.7%) affirmed that their school environments were adequately conducive to reading

Implications of the Findings

The findings dispel the unfounded belief that students' reading habit differ significantly between rural and urban secondary schools. They underscore the need for policy makers to view all students, regardless of school location, as equal beneficiaries of well-planned and effectively implemented educational policies. Sound policies begin with inclusive planning that consider both rural and urban contexts.

Furthermore, the results invite educational researchers to investigate the true factors behind the perceived academic advantage of urban students. They also remind teachers in rural areas not to underestimate their students but to help them realise their potentials through effective reading guidance. Achieving this requires strong motivation and support mechanisms from school leaders and government authorities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are provided to ensure that bountiful gains inherent in reading are maximised by all secondary school students:

- (i) Government, especially at state level, should set up necessary machineries that will adequately accommodate serious and compulsory reading across all secondary schools.
- (ii) There is the need to upgrade the existing libraries and establish new ones to encourage the students to widely read.
- (iii) School authorities should endeavour to inaugurate readers' club (where there is none) and strengthen it (where there is one); and ensure that every student is a member.
- (iv) Teachers in charge of reading should ensure that a period is devoted to the teaching of reading skill every week and motivate their students to engage in productive reading
- (v) Reading competitions should be organised and publicised at school, local, state and national levels. The competitions should be made alluring with fabulous prizes.
- (vi) Teachers, regardless their areas of specialisation, should endeavour to always motivate their students to read, at least, once daily.
- (vii) Parents need to play their own roles by providing de rigueur reading materials for their children/ wards, urging them to read daily and creating conducive environments at home for reading.
- (viii) Conclusively, there should be mass mobilisation towards reading.

REFERENCES

- Aina, J. A (2012). Reading habits of Nigerian University Students. *Journal of Educational Resesarch and Practice*, 2(1), 1 – 9.
- Akindele, O. (2016). Reading comprehension strategies and academic achievement of Nigerian secondary school students. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 6(2), 35 -44.
- Chika, J. O. (2009). An assessment of reading culture among students in tertiary institutions: A challenge to educational managers. *Report Geographic Code 6 NIGR*.
- Durotoye, A. (2011). Reading comprehension difficulties among Nigerian secondary school students. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 1(1), 34 – 1.
- Gambell, L. B.(1996). Creating an engaging classroom: A reading specialist’s perspective. *The Reading Teacher*, 50(2), 126 – 136.
- Guthrie, J. T. & Wigfeld, A. (2000). Engagement and motivation in reading. In M. L. Kamil, P. D. Pearson, & R. Moje (Eds.)’ *Handbook of Reading Research* (Vol. 3, pp. 403 – 422). Erlbaum.
- Hidi, S. & Renninger, K A. (2006). The four-phase model of interest development. *Educational Psychologist*, 41(2), 111 – 127.
- Krashen, S. (2004). The effect of reading on vocabulary development. *The Modern Language Journal*, 88(1), 1 – 8.
- Mabekoje, O. (2009). *Comprehensive language and communication studies: Pathfinder in language teaching methodology and communication enhancement*. Tunigraphic Prints.
- Obanya, P. (2002). Theories of reading and reading instruction. In P. Obanya (Ed.). ‘Reading and reading instruction in Nigeria’ (pp. 11 – 24). Heinemann Educational Books.
- Oyediran, O. O. (2019). Reading habits and academic performance among Nigerian secondary school students. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 9(1), 1 – 13.
- Sanders, M. (2007). Creating an optimum reading culture in the Low Countries: The role of stitching lezen. The National Platform for the Promotion of Reading in the Netherlands.

- Snowling, M. J. & Hulme, C. (2005). *The science of reading: A handbook*. Blackwell Publishing.
- Ukpeyong, A. E. (2017). Reading habits of Nigerian postgraduate students in digital age. *Journal of Educational Technology and Society*, 20(2), 141 – 151.
- Wigfield, A. & Guthrie, J. T. (1997). Relations of children's motivation for reading to the amount and breadth of their reading. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 89(3), 420 – 432.
- Yisa, A. O. (2008). Rubrics, phonics and sight-word instructional strategies and junior secondary school students' learning outcomes in reading comprehension (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis). Tai Solarin University of Education.